

Assessing the level of job satisfaction of administrative employees of St. Dominic College of Asia

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Abstract

This research aimed to determine the relationship between the perspective on salaries, benefits, and non-monetary remunerations of the administrative employees of St. Dominic College of Asia and their current job satisfaction. Involved in this study were all 80 administrative employees of St. Dominic College of Asia. The study was conducted in March 2018. A questionnaire was made consisting of the profiles of the administrative employees, perspectives on monetary and non-monetary compensations, level of job satisfaction, general opinion in the institution in which they are working and expected problems and possible solutions. The findings showed that there was no significant difference between the profiles of the administrative employee respondents and the lead variables. Company management may maintain a fair number of responsible and young administrative employees they can handle through recruitment and advertising shifts on working hours and training for career development.

Keywords: Job satisfaction; Administrative employees; St. Dominic College of Asia.

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Introduction

A significant percentage of people in developing countries work hard to acquire decent employment that will meet their needs. According to Ellickson and Logsdon (2002), job satisfaction refers to how much workers value their jobs. Job satisfaction, according to Schermerhorn (2011), is an emotional reaction to different aspects of an employee's employment. According to O'Reilly et al. (1991), job satisfaction is a subjective emotion that is shaped by an individual's impression of their place of employment. It can also refer to a worker's overall attitude toward work or their job. Hunter and Tietyen (1997) said that contented workers are more devoted and effective, and their happiness may have an impact on customer satisfaction and productivity at work.

Thus, the objective of this study is to examine the benefits, salaries, and other monetary remuneration that raise workers' job satisfaction levels at work. The extent to which an employee can be completely satisfied is not limited and can differ from person to person. The most significant indicator of a person's experience within an organization is their salary. Rewards play a significant role in enhancing an employee's job satisfaction and commitment. All benefits are considered reward determinants that an employee receives from their workplace (Malhotra et al., 2007). Reward is a vital factor that makes a big contribution towards enhancing job satisfaction and commitment. Organizations are expected to continuously improve their reward system to retain and make more productive employees.

Rewards refer to payments an employee receives in relation to his or her contribution to the organization, and these may come in the form of cash, noncash, or psychological benefits (Bratton & Gold, 2003). According to Newman et al. (2019), reward is another aspect of the employment relationship wherein workers receive tangible benefits and provisions. Among all incentives, monetary advantages are thought to be an important and constant component.

Typically, an established business views its ordinary workers as their primary source of improved efficiency. Contented workers are an organization's greatest asset. These workers are content with their jobs and tend to be more lively, passionate, motivated, and dedicated to their work (Syptak et al., 1999). Therefore, satisfaction is defined as a “*person’s feelings of pleasure or disappointment resulting from comparing a product’s perceived performance (or outcome) in relation to his or her expectations*” (Kotler & Keller, 2014). Therefore, the stress brought on by the discrepancy between an individual's expectations and unfulfilled requirements may be relieved by job satisfaction. Given the correlation between job satisfaction, employee work performance, and service quality, management needs to consider.

In this study, the chosen respondents are the administrative employees of St. Dominic College of Asia. They are given the chance to evaluate themselves regarding their job satisfaction level in terms of salaries, benefits, and non-monetary remunerations. Furthermore, the researchers will determine the necessary recommendations to increase the level of job satisfaction among their employees and help them maintain this to a high degree.

Literature Review

Frederick Herzberg suggested a study that was related to the theories of Maslow. The motivation-hygiene theory, which he developed, suggests that job pleasure may stem primarily from the task itself. His method resulted in the two-continuum model of job satisfaction, which ranked job satisfaction as the second most important factor. According to Herzberg’s view, there are several workplace elements that contribute to both job satisfaction and dissatisfaction. However, unsatisfactory work will be the consequence of poor hygiene factors. Cleaning up the bad hygiene, however, does not guarantee satisfaction. Similar to this, motivators are present in people who are happy in their jobs, but their absence does not guarantee their dissatisfaction. This means that the two-continuum model of Herzberg's Motivator-Hygiene Theory describes how job happiness essentially depends on the exterior features of the job itself, in connection to the job's ability to meet one’s higher-level demands of self-actualization (Sutter, 1996). Aside from the humanistic and financial benefits of job satisfaction studies, it has been shown to result in higher levels of organizational commitment, higher retention rates, and more productive employees (Green, 2000).

Several factors explain the empirical relationship between compensation and levels of research and development (R&D) activity (Clinch, 1991). The analysis found that high and low R&D firms offered different explicit compensation arrangements. It also investigated how R&D affects the relationship between total remuneration and performance metrics based on stock and accounting. A different study (Carrasco-Hernandez & Sánchez-Marin, 2007) made a distinction between employee compensation in family-owned and managed businesses and non-family and professionally managed businesses. This is an important finding because, since the compensation elements are clearly stated according to risk sharing and the interests of the owners, chief executive officers (CEOs), and employees, understanding the role of concentrated ownership and management structure in the company is necessary to recognize the employee compensation design. It also reveals that a number of factors have had their connections to job satisfaction. These variables include internal employment characteristics (like working conditions, salary, and supervision) as well as demographic information (like age, gender, and race).

Tansel and Gazioğlu (2013) used the linked employer-employee survey data in Britain to examine job satisfaction in connection to managerial views toward employees and business size. Large companies have less satisfactory management-employee interactions. There is evidence, though, that larger companies are making an effort to make up for their considerable size by holding frequent discussions about the need for training, potential career advancement, and compensation-related matters. Weak management-employee interactions are a major reason why work satisfaction is typically lower in large organizations. These findings have significant implications for policy for business managers, especially in the context of management-employee relations in large companies. Enhancing management-employee interactions in large companies would boost productivity and lower turnover, in addition to raising employee satisfaction in a number of areas.

Hodge (2011) investigated variables associated with internal audit function job dissatisfaction. The study also looked into the possible causes of internal auditors' apparent job dissatisfaction. To develop workers who are happy with their work and feel a sense of responsibility, it is critical to identify and comprehend the elements that lead to internal audit employees' dissatisfaction. This will help reduce attrition, which has a direct connection to employee dissatisfaction. The results showed that age and attrition rate had a substantial impact on job satisfaction among internal auditor participants, but career choice had no discernible effect.

The contentment of employees plays a crucial role in the growth of any enterprise. High levels of happiness might lead to better performance and efficacy when carrying out tasks or providing services. Every employer should prioritize their employees' well-being. There are more opportunities to keep good workers in the company and to have effective workforce coordination if the demands and requirements of the employees are met. This could therefore result in higher productivity levels within the organization (Angeles et al., 2015).

To protect the welfare of contract workers, the government, labor unions, and employers may implement stronger and more noticeable support systems. For workers with families, compensation and advancement are the most important factors (Nisola-Blance & Menes, 2014). It is necessary for management to identify certain factors so that they can design programs that would improve the level of job satisfaction among employees.

Also, it is to be noted that the high organizational commitment of employees may be considered by the management in devising new ways to make the employees develop a stronger feeling of attachment towards the organization. The management can provide training, engagement, incentives, and a better working environment to improve job satisfaction and strengthen organizational commitment. Unfortunately, only a small percentage of employees are aware of the rational and sound pay systems that many organizations have in place (Menchavez, 2003). Employers can avoid employee discontent and clear any misunderstandings by making an effort to clarify these policies.

A study by Degracia et al. (2015) suggested that the level of job satisfaction of professionals affects one's professionalism at work. It is said that professionalism is the key to quality and efficiency in achieving organizational goals. It is more than mere compliance with rules and regulations in their field of work. Professionalism is adherence to the ethical standards governing the profession, and the primary concern of being a professional is public service. Hence, it is important to also know the perception of the people towards their line of work.

Statement of the Problem

This research aimed to determine the relationship between the perspective on salaries, benefits, and non-monetary remunerations of the administrative employees of St. Dominic College of Asia and their current job satisfaction. Specifically, the study endeavored to answer the following:

1. What is the profile of the administrative employees at St. Dominic College of Asia in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. Age;
 - 1.2. Gender;
 - 1.3. Civil Status;
 - 1.4. Highest Educational Attainment;
 - 1.5. Length of Service; and,
 - 1.6. Estimated Average Monthly Income?
2. How do the respondents perceive the compensations and benefits from their work (Social Security System Contribution; National Health Insurance Program Contribution; Contribution to Home Development and Mutual Fund; and Bonuses and Rewards) in terms of the following:
 - 2.1. Awareness;
 - 2.2. Sufficiency; and
 - 2.3. Availability?
3. How do the respondents perceive their job satisfaction as employees in terms of the following:
 - 3.1. Satisfaction with Job;
 - 3.2. Satisfaction with Shift;
 - 3.3. Satisfaction with Training and Career Development;
 - 3.4. Satisfaction with Employee Compensation; and,
 - 3.5. Organizational Commitment?
4. What is the general opinion of the respondents about their job?
5. What are the problems encountered and possible solutions thereto?
6. Is there any significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and the lead variables?

Methodology

This study applied the descriptive research method to obtain information about existing conditions needed in the chosen field of study. This method enabled the researchers to infer the theoretical meaning of their findings and develop hypotheses for further studies. The process of descriptive research in this study involves the gathering and tabulation of data, as well as the analysis and interpretation of the obtained data. Moreover, several variables were considered to help the researchers analyze the different factors involved in this study. Thus, description is merged with comparison or contrast, including measurement, classification, analysis, and interpretation. The variables include the profile of the employee respondents, the salaries and wages, other compensation and benefits: Social Security System (SSS), National Health Insurance Program (PhilHealth), Home Development Mutual Fund (HDMF or PAG-IBIG) contributions, other agency loans, bonuses and rewards, the employees' job satisfaction: as to the job itself, as to the employees' shift, as to their training and career development, as to the employee compensation, and their organizational commitment, the employees' general opinion, and the problems and their possible solutions.

Respondents

The researchers gathered information from 100 administrative employees of St. Dominic College of Asia. All of the employees were from the different administrative departments of the institution, e.g., Accounting, Human Resources, Registrar, Finance, Auditing, and Admissions Departments. The researchers opted to use 80 percent of the administrative employee population. From the sample size of 80 administrative employees, only 26 were males and the rest were females. Most of the respondents are married and college graduates. These employees were asked to evaluate themselves regarding their job satisfaction level. The researchers randomly disseminated copies of questionnaires, all of which were completed and submitted for analysis.

Sampling Technique

The information obtained from the participants has been tallied and analyzed. The 5% marginal error served as the foundation for the researchers. The overall sample size is 80 out of the 100 employees in the whole population, according to the formula. Thus, the researchers opted to gather data from the 80 employees so that the information collected could be sufficient.

Research Instruments

The instruments used in this study were questionnaires. The researchers carried out the study using self-made questionnaires, some of which were adopted from other studies. A thorough analysis of the questions was conducted, keeping those that were pertinent to the subject and replacing the others with better ones. The questionnaires were properly formatted by the researchers to allow for the collection of relevant and adequate data from the respondents.

The questionnaire for the employee respondents was divided into five parts. The first part focused on the profile of respondents. The second part focused on the compensation and benefits given to the employee, which were subdivided into six subtopics, namely: salaries and wages, compensation and benefits, which include Social Security System (SSS), National Health Insurance Program (PhilHealth), Home Development and Mutual Fund (HDMF or PAG-IBIG) contributions, other agency loans, and bonuses and rewards. The third part concentrated on the job satisfaction of the employee, which was further subdivided into five subtopics, namely: satisfaction with the job, satisfaction with the shift, satisfaction with training and career development, satisfaction with employee compensation, and organizational commitment. The fourth part was dedicated to the respondents' general opinion about their current job. The last part focused on the problems encountered and the possible solutions in relation to the compensations, benefits, and job satisfaction levels of the employees of St. Dominic College of Asia.

Validation of the Instrument

The capacity of a question to distinguish between respondents who differ in their level of familiarity with and proficiency with the content being assessed is the most reliable indicator of its efficacy. The researchers employed item analysis to assess the questionnaire's validity. It is a process that was used to calculate each test item's validity index (VI) and difficulty index (DI). Following the study of the items, a choice was made regarding which questions or things should be kept, changed, thrown out, or replaced. Questions that were highly discriminating were kept, whereas questions that were moderately discriminating were changed. Even questions that had a non-discriminating validity index were eliminated.

Twenty samples that were provided to the relevant study participants were used by the researchers to assess the survey's validity. The researchers first determined the proportion of respondents who answered "strongly agree" and those who answered "strongly disagree" for each question. The validity index that was applied to the results' interpretation made a difference. The majority of the interpretation's results showed strong discrimination, indicating the validity of the questionnaire.

The technique used by the researchers in determining reliability was the Split-Half Method. This was done by dividing the total set of items into halves and using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation to measure the association between the responses. The split-half reliability has been applied to the questionnaire in order to assess its reliability. After dividing the questionnaires into even and odd-numbered sections, the researchers calculated the rankings using the Spearman's correlation formula. The test's correlation coefficient served as the foundation for the reliability assessment. The internal consistency test of the questions was applied.

The correlation between two variables, x and y , evaluated on a similar relationship was the first thing the researchers focused on. Using Spearman's Brown prophecy, a high relationship was interpreted since the r_{sb} resulted in 0.8502. The coefficient represented the study's questionnaire's overall efficacy and reliability.

Data Gathering

From March 19 to 23, 2018, the researchers disseminated 80 copies of survey questionnaires to the administrative employees of St. Dominic College of Asia in Cavite, Philippines. A total of 80 questionnaire copies were completed. The frequency of items checked by the respondents' data contribution was used to compute and tabulate the results. Several statistical approaches were used to interpret the results following the data tabulation. The researchers refined the outcomes of the data collection methods for interpretation.

Statistical Treatment

Based on the challenges identified and the research strategy, the data gathered for this study were categorized and arranged. The data were later coded, tallied, and tabulated to facilitate the presentation and interpretation of the results.

1. Likert Scale: This was applied to change the respondents' responses. Strongly Agree, Agree, Undecided, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree are choices on the 5-point scale. It was requested of the respondents to check the spaces assigned to each selection. The numerical value of 1 to 5 denotes each Likert item. The weighted mean computation would establish the overall designated value. Each Likert item has a scoring system that shows that a response is more favorable the higher the score and more unfavorable the lower the score.

Table 1. Likert scale

Scale Value	Range	Interpretation
5	4.21-5.00	Strongly Agree
4	3.41-4.20	Agree
3	2.61-3.40	Undecided
2	1.81-2.60	Disagree
1	1.00-1.80	Strongly Disagree

2. Frequency and Percentage: The respondents were categorized based on personal background factors, including age, gender, marital status, highest level of education attained, and average monthly income, using the percentage and frequency distribution.

3. Ranking: It is used for comparing variables and for sharing the importance of the items analyzed.

4. Weighted Mean: It serves to figure out the average responses to the numerous options given in the different sections of the survey questionnaire that are utilized.

5. Pearson r Product-Moment Correlation: It determines the direction and degree of relationship between two variables (whether positive or negative).

6. ANOVA (One-Way Analysis of Variance): This was done to ascertain whether there was a substantial difference between the respondents' profile and the chosen variables. It is employed to determine whether a difference between two or more means that were derived from separate samples differs significantly.

Results and Discussion

Profile of the Administrative Employees of St. Dominic College of Asia

The profile was limited only to six (6) variables, namely: (a) age, (b) gender, (c) civil status, (d) highest educational attainment, (e) length of service, and (f) estimated average monthly income.

Table 2. Profile of the administrative employees (n=80)

Profile	Category	Frequency	Percentage	Ranking
Age (in years)	18-29	68	85.00%	1
	30-39	6	7.5%	2
	40-49	5	6.25%	3
	50 and above	1	1.25%	4
Gender	Male	26	32.50%	2
	Female	54	67.50%	1
Civil Status	Single	62	77.50%	1
	Married	18	22.50%	2
Highest Educational Attainment	College Undergraduate	10	12.50%	2
	College Graduate	69	86.25%	1
	Advanced	1	1.25%	3
Length of Service	Less than 1 year	30	37.50%	2
	1-3 years	40	50.00%	1
	4-6 years	8	10.00%	3
	7-9 years	1	1.25%	4.5
	13-15 years	1	1.25%	4.5
Estimated Average Monthly Income	Below P5,000	7	8.75%	3
	P8,001-P11,000	16	20.00%	2
	P11,001-P14,000	5	6.25%	4
	P14,001-P17,000	42	52.50%	1
	P17,001-P20,000	8	10.00%	3
	Above P20,000	2	2.50%	5

Based on the table above, in terms of age, the age bracket of 18 to 29 years old represents the highest frequency at 85%, or 68 respondents. Six respondents belong to the age bracket of 30 to 39 years old, followed by five respondents belonging to the age bracket of 40 to 49 years old and one respondent belonging to the age bracket 50 years old and older, which was equivalent to 1.25%. This may infer that the administrative employees of SDCA are young professionals.

In terms of gender, the table presents female employees, consisting of 54 employees, representing 67.50% of the total respondents. Meanwhile, 26 employees were male, representing 32.50% of the total respondents. This means that the majority of the administrative employees at SDCA are female. In terms of civil status, most of the respondents are single, with a frequency of 62, or 77.50%, while respondents who are married represent 22.50%, or a frequency of 18.

In terms of educational attainment, it shows that 69 (86.25%) of 80 respondents attained a bachelor's degree. On the other hand, 10 (6.67%) of 75 respondents are college undergraduates, and one, or 1.25%, of the total respondents has a master's degree. It can be inferred that the majority of them managed to attain a bachelor's degree. In terms of length of service, it shows that the greatest number of respondents have been with the company for one (1) to three (3) years, with a frequency of 40, or 50.00%. Next in the rank are those who are in service less than one (1) year, with a frequency of 30 (37.50%). The bracket for respondents working in the company for four (4) to six (6) years ranked third, with a frequency of 8 or 10.00%. Lastly, those who have been in service for seven (7) to nine (9) years and 13 to 15 years ranked fourth, with a frequency of one or 1.25% each. This shows that most of the administrative employees of SDCA serve the company for one (1) to three (3) years.

In terms of average monthly income, it shows that 42 (52.50%) of 80 respondents have an estimated average monthly income of P14,001 to P17,000, which represents the majority. There are 16 respondents who have an estimated average monthly income of P8,001 to P11,000, which is equivalent to 20%. There are eight respondents with an estimated average monthly income of P17,001 to P20,000, and seven respondents have an estimated average monthly income of below P5,000. Five respondents, or 6.25%, have an estimated average monthly income of P11,001 to P14,000. Lastly, two (2.50%) of 75 respondents have an estimated average monthly income of above P20,000.

Perspective on Monetary and Non-Monetary Benefits

Table 3. Weighted mean and verbal interpretation relative to monetary and non-monetary benefits as to awareness

Awareness	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I fully understand the nature of the deductions in my salary.	4.39	Strongly Agree
2. I fully understand the nature of Social Security System (SSS).	4.39	Strongly Agree
3. I fully understand the nature of PhilHealth Contribution.	4.48	Strongly Agree
4. I fully understand the nature of Pag-IBIG Contribution.	4.37	Strongly Agree
5. I believe that I deserve the bonus that I am getting.	4.17	Agree
Weighted Mean	4.36	Strongly Agree

Table 3 demonstrates the weighted mean and verbal interpretation from the perspective of monetary and non-monetary awareness. The table illustrates that the respondents strongly agree that employees fully understand the nature of PhilHealth Contribution (4.48); fully understand the nature of the deductions in their salary (4.39); fully understand the nature of the Social Security System (4.39); and fully understand the nature of Pag-IBIG Contribution (4.37). On the other hand, respondents agreed that they deserve the bonus that they are getting (4.17). The weighted mean is 4.36.

Table 4. Weighted mean and verbal interpretation relative to monetary and non-monetary benefits as to sufficiency

Sufficiency	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I am generally satisfied with the salary I am getting.	2.83	Undecided
2. I am generally satisfied with the amounts of deductions in my salary.	3.65	Agree
3. The salary I am receiving is sufficient for my daily living.	2.80	Undecided
4. I am satisfied with the benefits that I will receive from SSS.	3.76	Agree
5. I am satisfied with the benefits that I will receive from PhilHealth.	3.87	Agree
6. I am satisfied with the benefits that I will receive from Pag-IBIG.	3.83	Agree
7. Loans can answer the financial needs in times of crisis.	3.46	Agree
8. I am generally satisfied with the bonus that I am getting.	3.26	Undecided
Weighted Mean	3.43	Agree

Table 4 exhibits the weighted mean and verbal interpretation of the perspective relative to monetary and non-monetary benefits as to sufficiency. The table shows that the respondents agree that they are satisfied with the benefits that they will receive from PhilHealth (3.87); they are satisfied with the benefits that they will receive from Pag-IBIG (3.83); they are satisfied with the benefits that they will receive from SSS (3.76); they are generally satisfied with the amounts of deductions in their salary (3.65); and loans can answer their financial needs in times of crisis (3.46). The respondents are undecided with regard to the bonus that they are getting (3.26); they are generally satisfied with the salary they are getting (2.83); and the salary they are receiving is sufficient for their daily living (2.80). The average weighted mean is 3.43.

Table 5. Weighted mean and verbal interpretation relative to monetary and non-monetary benefits as to availability

Availability	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I am assured that I will receive the benefits from SSS.	3.96	Agree
2. Discounts from hospitalization can easily be availed.	3.91	Agree
3. Loan requirements are strictly implemented.	3.74	Agree
4. Pag-IBIG loan is released immediately upon submission of request.	3.59	Agree
5. Company loan requirements are strictly implemented.	3.80	Agree
6. Company loan can answer the financial needs at the time of crisis.	3.39	Undecided
7. There is no delay in receiving my bonuses.	3.54	Agree
Weighted Mean	3.70	Agree

Table 5 illustrates the weighted mean and verbal interpretation relative to monetary and non-monetary benefits as to availability. The table shows that the respondents are assured they will receive the benefits from SSS (3.96); discounts from hospitalization can be easily availed (3.91); company loan requirements are strictly implemented (3.80); loan requirements are strictly implemented (3.74); Pag-IBIG loan is released immediately upon submission of request (3.59); and there is no delay in receiving their bonuses (3.54). The respondents are undecided as to whether the company loan can meet their financial needs in times of crisis (3.39). The weighted mean is 3.70.

Job Satisfaction

Table 6. Weighted mean and verbal interpretation relative to the job satisfaction of employees through their satisfaction with their job itself

Satisfaction with Job	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Generally speaking, I am very satisfied with this job.	3.87	Agree
2. I am generally satisfied with the kind of work I do in this job.	3.87	Agree
3. I do not usually think of quitting this job.	3.48	Agree
4. Most people on this job are very satisfied with the job.	3.33	Undecided
5. People on this job do not usually think of quitting.	3.26	Undecided
Weighted Mean	3.56	Agree

Table 6 shows that the respondents agreed that they are very satisfied with their job (3.87); they are satisfied with the kind of work they do in their job (3.87); they do not usually think of quitting their job (3.48); the respondents are undecided that most people on their job are very satisfied with it (3.33); people on this job do not usually think of quitting (3.26). The weighted mean is 3.56.

Table 7. Weighted mean and verbal interpretation relative to the job satisfaction of employees through their satisfaction with their shift

Satisfaction with Shift	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I am generally satisfied with the shift of my work hours.	4.28	Strongly Agree
2. Most people in my shift are very satisfied with their shift.	4.17	Agree
3. People in this shift often do not think of changing their work hour shift.	3.96	Agree
Weighted Mean	4.14	Agree

Table 7 shows that the respondents strongly agree that they are generally satisfied with the shift in their job (4.28). Most of them agreed that most of the people in their shift are very satisfied with it (4.17), and people in their shift often do not think of changing their work hours (3.96). The weighted mean is 4.14.

Table 8. Weighted mean and verbal interpretation relative to the job satisfaction of employees through their satisfaction with their training and career development

Satisfaction with Training and Career Development	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I am satisfied with the training I underwent or am undergoing.	3.78	Agree
2. Most people on this job are satisfied with the training they underwent or are undergoing.	3.61	Agree
3. There are many opportunities for promotion and improvement.	3.48	Agree
4. My supervisors are helping me in my development.	3.74	Agree
Weighted Mean	3.65	Agree

Table 8 shows that the respondents are satisfied with the training they underwent or are undergoing (3.78); their supervisors are helping them in their development (3.74); and most people on this job are satisfied with the training they underwent or are undergoing (3.61). The respondents are undecided about whether there are many opportunities for promotion and improvement. The weighted mean is 3.65.

Table 9. Weighted mean and verbal interpretation relative to the job satisfaction of employees through their satisfaction with their compensation

Satisfaction with Compensation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I am satisfied with the benefits that I get from the company.	3.39	Undecided
2. I am generally satisfied with the salary I am getting.	3.02	Undecided
3. I am generally satisfied with the privileges I get from the company.	3.33	Undecided
Weighted Mean	3.25	Undecided

Table 9 shows that the respondents are undecided as to whether they are satisfied with the benefits they get from the company (3.39); they are generally satisfied with the privileges they get from the company (3.33); and they are satisfied with the salary they are getting. The weighted mean is 3.25.

Table 10. Weighted mean and verbal interpretation relative to the job satisfaction of employees through their satisfaction with their compensation

Satisfaction with Compensation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. They offer of a little more money with another company would not seriously make me think of changing jobs.	3.33	Undecided
2. I am quite proud to be able to tell people the company in which I work for.	3.67	Agree
3. My life would be greatly disrupted if I left my present job.	3.00	Undecided
4. I feel emotionally connected to the company for which I work for.	3.43	Agree
5. My employer would be so disappointed if I left my job.	3.20	Undecided
6. At this point, I will stay more on my job because I want to, not because I have to.	3.46	Agree
7. I feel like I am part of the family on the company in which I work for.	3.67	Agree
8. I will stay on my job because people would think poorly of me for leaving.	2.67	Undecided
9. I have other choice, but I chose to stay on my present job.	3.67	Agree
10. I feel like I strongly belong to my organization.	3.74	Agree
11. I feel a strong obligation to stay on my job.	3.70	Agree
Weighted Mean	3.41	Agree

Table 10 shows that the respondents feel like they strongly belong to their organization (3.74); feel a strong obligation to stay on their job (3.70); are quite proud to be able to tell people the company in which they work (3.67); feel like they are part of the family in the company they work for (3.67); have other choices but they chose to stay on their present job (3.67); will stay more on their job because they want to, not because they have to (3.46); and feel emotionally connected to the company in which they work (3.43). The respondents are undecided as to whether an offer of a little more money with another company would not seriously make them think of changing jobs (3.33); their employer would be disappointed if they left their job (3.20); their life would be greatly disrupted if they left their present job (3.00); they will stay on their job because people would think poorly of them for leaving (2.67). The weighted mean is 3.41.

General Opinion on Benefits

Table 11 shows that the respondents agreed that there is no delay in giving their salary (3.91); loan requirements are strictly implemented (3.89); approval of loan depends on the number of their actual contributions (3.74); credit investigations are conducted upon submission of complete loan requirements (3.72); they can easily approach the management (3.65); the company is fully aware that the bonuses and rewards given to deserving employees are accountable and reasonable (3.63); immediate supervisors are essential in developing their skills and attitudes (3.63); the organization let them feel that they belong or are part of the company in which they work for (3.61); they fully understand the deductions in their salaries (3.57); the company is conducting trainings for them before they are put on the job (3.52); employees in their company are satisfied with the training they underwent or they are undergoing (3.52); employees in their company are generally satisfied with the rights and privileges they get from the company (3.52); they feel that they are emotionally connected to the company they work for (3.52); and the company is satisfied with the people they hired or employed (3.50); the financial assistance to them are released immediately (3.46); and previous and unpaid loans may be waived in favor of benefits due to a particular emerging case (3.41).

The respondents are undecided if they are satisfied with their respective working hours (3.46); it is possible for them to avail of more than one assistance at any given time (3.37); the company is taking into account the sufficiency of their daily living allowance (3.37); most of the employees are satisfied with their respective jobs (3.37); employees do not usually think of changing their work hour shift (3.35); the company can provide reasonable compensation demands of the employees (3.30); employees are satisfied with the benefits they are getting (3.30); there are no complaints about their performance (3.28); the company is providing many opportunities for promotion and rewards (3.26); that it will be disappointing if some employees will leave the organization (3.26); that there are no complaints with regards to their salaries (3.09); that employees within the organization do not usually think of quitting in their jobs (3.09); employees of the company are satisfied with the salary they are getting (2.98). The weighted mean is 3.46.

Table 11. Weighted mean and verbal interpretation relative to general opinion on benefits

Benefits	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Employees of the company are satisfied with the salary they are getting.	2.98	Undecided
2. There is no delay in giving the salary of the employees.	3.91	Agree
3. The company can provide reasonable compensation demands of the employees.	3.30	Undecided
4. Financial assistances to the employees are released immediately.	3.46	Agree
5. Employees are satisfied with the benefits they are getting.	3.30	Undecided
6. Employees fully understand the deductions in their salaries.	3.57	Agree
7. Previous and unpaid loans may be waived in favor of benefits due to a particular emerging case.	3.41	Agree
8. It is possible for employees to avail of more than one assistance at any given time.	3.37	Undecided
9. Loan requirements are strictly implemented.	3.89	Agree
10. Credit investigations are conducted upon submission of complete	3.72	Agree

loan requirements.		
11. Approval of loan depends on the number of actual contributions of employees.	3.74	Agree
12. There are no complaints exists with regards to employees' salaries.	3.09	Undecided
13. The company is considering the sufficiency of the employees' daily living allowance.	3.37	Undecided
14. The company is fully aware that the bonuses and rewards given to the deserving employees are accountable and reasonable.	3.63	Agree
15. Employees can easily approach the management.	3.65	Agree
16. The company is conducting trainings for the employees before they are put on the job.	3.52	Agree
17. The company is satisfied with the people hired or employed.	3.50	Agree
18. There are no complaints about the employees' performance.	3.28	Undecided
19. Most of the employees are satisfied with their respective jobs.	3.37	Undecided
20. Employees within the organization do not usually think of quitting in their jobs.	3.09	Undecided
21. Generally, employees are satisfied with their respective working hours.	3.46	Undecided
22. Employees do not usually think of changing their work hour shift.	3.35	Undecided
23. Employees are satisfied with the training they already underwent or are undergoing.	3.52	Agree
24. The company is providing many opportunities for promotion and rewards.	3.26	Undecided
25. Immediate supervisors are essential in developing the employees' skills and attitudes.	3.63	Agree
26. The employees are generally satisfied with the rights and privileges they get from the company.	3.52	Agree
27. The employees feel that they are emotionally connected to the company for which they work.	3.52	Agree
28. It will be disappointing if some employees will leave the organization.	3.26	Undecided
29. The organization let its employees feel that they belong or are part of the family at the company in which they work for.	3.61	Agree
Weighted Mean	3.46	Undecided

Problems and Possible Solutions

Table 12. Weighted mean and verbal interpretation relative to problems encountered by the employees

Encountered Problems	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I am currently having problem about my salary condition.	3.48	Agree
2. I am currently having problem about my employee benefits.	3.00	Undecided
3. I am currently having problem about my bonuses and rewards.	3.22	Undecided
4. I am currently having problem about my rights and privileges.	3.07	Undecided
5. I am currently having problem about my work environment.	2.98	Undecided
Weighted Mean	3.15	Undecided

Table 12 shows that the respondents are having problems about their respective salary condition. For the rest of the items, the respondents are undecided, with a weighted mean of 3.15.

Table 13. Weighted mean and verbal interpretation relative to possible solutions

Possible Solutions	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I need a salary increase, if permitted.	4.20	Agree
2. The processing time for salaries, benefits, and bonuses must be minimized.	3.89	Agree
3. Given rewards, rights and privileges to the administrative employees must be carefully reviewed periodically.	4.24	Strongly Agree
4. I want a better working environment for my current job.	4.02	Agree
5. I want a more controllable shift in my job.	3.67	Agree
Weighted Mean	4.00	Agree

Table 13 shows that the administrative employees of SDCA strongly agreed that the given rewards, rights, and privileges to the employees must be carefully reviewed periodically, with a computed weighted mean of 4.24. The administrative employees agree that they need a salary increase, if permitted; the processing time for salaries, benefits, and bonuses must be minimized, with computed weighted means of 4.20 and 3.89. The employees want a better working environment and a more controllable shift in their current job, with a weighted mean of 4.02 and 3.67, respectively.

Significant Difference between the Profile and the Perspective of the Company and the Lead Variables

Table 14. Significant difference between the age of the respondents and the lead variables

Variables	r Value	Critical Value	Significance	Decision
A. Compensation and Benefits				
1.1 Awareness	0.311	2.725	Not Significant	Accept H_0
1.2 Sufficiency	14.716	2.725	Significant	Reject H_0
1.3 Availability	3.060	2.725	Significant	Accept H_0
B. Job Satisfaction				
2.1 Satisfaction with Job	3.414	2.725	Significant	Reject H_0
2.2 Satisfaction with Shift	1.576	2.725	Not Significant	Accept H_0
2.3 Satisfaction with Training and Career Development	2.699	2.725	Not Significant	Accept H_0
2.4 Satisfaction with Employer Compensation	1.789	2.725	Not Significant	Accept H_0
2.5 Organizational Commitment	2.797	2.725	Significant	Reject H_0
C. General Opinion	0.776	2.725	Not Significant	Accept H_0
D. Problems Encountered	0.339	2.725	Not Significant	Accept H_0
E. Possible Solutions	0.515	2.725	Not Significant	Accept H_0

Table 14 presents the significant difference between the age of the respondents and the lead variables. The table shows that there is no significant difference between the age of the respondents and the lead variables, except for sufficiency, availability, satisfaction with the job, and organizational commitment. This is evidenced by the critical value of 2.725, which is greater than the r values of 0.311, 1.576, 2.699, 1.789, 0.776, 0.339, and 0.515. This results in the acceptance of the null hypothesis. On the other hand, the difference between the age of the respondents and sufficiency, availability, satisfaction with the job, and organizational commitment is significant. This is evidenced by the critical value of 2.725, which is less than the r value with a range of 2.797 to 14.716 as seen in the table, thus rejecting the null hypothesis.

Table 15. Significant difference between the gender of the respondents and the lead variables

Variables	r Value	Critical Value	Significance	Decision
A. Compensation and Benefits				
1.1 Awareness	2.516	3.963	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
1.2 Sufficiency	1.864	3.963	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
1.3 Availability	2.739	3.963	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
B. Job Satisfaction				
2.1 Satisfaction with Job	2.379	3.963	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
2.2 Satisfaction with Shift	1.778	3.963	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
2.3 Satisfaction with Training and Career Development	3.804	3.963	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
2.4 Satisfaction with Employer Compensation	6.571	3.963	Significant	Reject H ₀
2.5 Organizational Commitment	11.37	3.963	Significant	Reject H ₀
C. General Opinion	0.201	3.963	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
D. Problems Encountered	0.232	3.963	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
E. Possible Solutions	0.396	3.963	Not Significant	Accept H ₀

Table 15 presents the significant difference between the gender of the respondents and the lead variables. The table shows that there is no significant difference between the gender of the respondents and the lead variables, except for satisfaction with employer compensation and organizational commitment. This is evidenced by the critical value of 3.963, which is greater than the r values of 2.516, 1.864, 2.739, 1.778, 3.804, 0.201, 0.232, and 0.396, respectively. This results in the acceptance of the null hypothesis. On the other hand, the difference between the gender of the respondents and satisfaction with employer compensation and organizational commitment is significant. This is evidenced by the critical value of 3.963, which is less than the r values of 6.571 and 11.370, thus rejecting the null hypothesis.

Table 16. Significant difference between the civil status of the respondents and the lead variables

Variables	r Value	Critical Value	Significance	Decision
A. Compensation and Benefits				
1.1 Awareness	0.291	3.963	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
1.2 Sufficiency	0.003	3.963	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
1.3 Availability	0.179	3.963	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
B. Job Satisfaction				
2.1 Satisfaction with Job	0.010	3.963	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
2.2 Satisfaction with Shift	0.065	3.963	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
2.3 Satisfaction with Training and Career Development	0.019	3.963	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
2.4 Satisfaction with Employer Compensation	0.307	3.963	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
2.5 Organizational Commitment	0.534	3.963	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
C. General Opinion	1.019	3.963	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
D. Problems Encountered	1.205	3.963	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
E. Possible Solutions	0.427	3.963	Not Significant	Accept H ₀

Table 16 shows the significant difference between the civil status of the respondents and the lead variables. The table shows that there is no significant difference between the civil status of the respondents and the lead variables. This is evidenced by the critical value of 3.963, which is greater than the r values of 0.291, 0.003, 0.179, 0.010, 0.065, 0.019, 0.307, 0.534, 1.019, 1.205, and 0.427, respectively. This results in the acceptance of the null hypothesis.

Table 17. Significant difference between the highest educational attainment of the respondents and the lead variables

Variables	r Value	Critical Value	Significance	Decision
A. Compensation and Benefits				
1.1 Awareness	0.533	3.115	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
1.2 Sufficiency	7.552	3.115	Significant	Reject H ₀
1.3 Availability	5.305	3.115	Significant	Reject H ₀
B. Job Satisfaction				
2.1 Satisfaction with Job	0.010	3.115	Significant	Reject H ₀
2.2 Satisfaction with Shift	0.065	3.115	Significant	Reject H ₀
2.3 Satisfaction with Training and Career Development	0.019	3.115	Significant	Reject H ₀
2.4 Satisfaction with Employer Compensation	0.307	3.115	Significant	Reject H ₀
2.5 Organizational Commitment	0.534	3.115	Significant	Reject H ₀
C. General Opinion	1.019	3.115	Significant	Reject H ₀
D. Problems Encountered	1.205	3.115	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
E. Possible Solutions	0.427	3.115	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
F. Compensations and Benefits and Job Satisfaction	1.988	3.115	Not Significant	Accept H ₀

Table 17 presents the significant difference between the highest educational attainment of the respondents and the lead variables. The table shows that there is no significant difference between the highest educational attainment of the respondents and the lead variables. This is evidenced by the critical value of 3.115, which is greater than the r values of 0.533, 0.455, 0.104, and 1.988, respectively. This results in the acceptance of the null hypothesis. On the other hand, the difference between the highest educational attainment of the respondents and satisfaction with employer compensation and organizational commitment is significant. This is evidenced by the critical value of 3.115, which is less than the r value with a range of 3.147 to 7.552, thus rejecting the null hypothesis.

Table 18. Significant difference between the length of service of the respondents and the lead variables

Variables	r Value	Critical Value	Significance	Decision
A. Compensation and Benefits				
1.1 Awareness	1.861	2.494	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
1.2 Sufficiency	0.963	2.494	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
1.3 Availability	0.684	2.494	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
B. Job Satisfaction				
2.1 Satisfaction with Job	0.630	2.494	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
2.2 Satisfaction with Shift	0.435	2.494	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
2.3 Satisfaction with Training and Career Development	1.096	2.494	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
2.4 Satisfaction with Employer Compensation	0.759	2.494	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
2.5 Organizational Commitment	0.645	2.494	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
C. General Opinion	0.785	2.494	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
D. Problems Encountered	0.247	2.494	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
E. Possible Solutions	0.217	2.494	Not Significant	Accept H ₀

Table 18 shows that there is no significant difference between the length of service of the respondents and the lead variables. This is evidenced by the critical value of 2.494, which is greater than the r values with a range of 0.217 to 1.861, respectively. This results in the acceptance of the null hypothesis.

Table 19. Significant difference between the estimated average monthly income of the respondents and the lead variables

Variables	r Value	Critical Value	Significance	Decision
A. Compensation and Benefits				
1.1 Awareness	0.483	2.340	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
1.2 Sufficiency	18.321	2.340	Significant	Reject H ₀
1.3 Availability	10.952	2.340	Significant	Reject H ₀
B. Job Satisfaction				
2.1 Satisfaction with Job	9.149	2.340	Significant	Reject H ₀
2.2 Satisfaction with Shift	5.587	2.340	Significant	Reject H ₀
2.3 Satisfaction with Training and Career Development	6.792	2.340	Significant	Reject H ₀
2.4 Satisfaction with Employer Compensation	4.386	2.340	Significant	Reject H ₀
2.5 Organizational Commitment	4.954	2.340	Significant	Reject H ₀
C. General Opinion	1.278	2.340	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
D. Problems Encountered	1.249	2.340	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
E. Possible Solutions	1.479	2.340	Not Significant	Accept H ₀

Table 19 shows that there is no significant difference between the estimated average monthly income of the respondents and the lead variables, except for sufficiency, availability, satisfaction with job, satisfaction with shift, satisfaction with training and career development, satisfaction with employer compensation, and organizational commitment. This is evidenced by the critical value of 2.340, which is greater than the r values with a range of 0.438 to 1.479, respectively. This results in the acceptance of the null hypothesis. On the other hand, there is a significant difference between the estimated average monthly income of the respondents and sufficiency, availability, satisfaction with the job, satisfaction with the shift, satisfaction with training and career development, satisfaction with employer compensation, and organizational commitment. This is evidenced by the critical value of 2.340, which is less than the r value with a range of 4.386 to 18.321, respectively, thus rejecting the null hypothesis.

Conclusion and Recommendations

After applying the appropriate statistical tools to the data gathered and analyzing the results thereon, the findings were revealed. The majority of the respondents belong to the age bracket of 18 to 29 years old, are female, single, college graduates, and are one (1) to three (3) years in service, with an estimated average monthly income of P14,001 to P17,000. The respondents agreed on awareness and availability and are undecided on sufficiency. The respondents agree on satisfaction with the job, satisfaction with the shift, satisfaction with training and career development, and are undecided on satisfaction with employer compensation and organizational commitment on all items listed.

The respondents are undecided in terms of the generalized opinion of administrative employees associated with perspective on compensation and benefit packages and perspective on job satisfaction based on all the listed information. With regard to problems encountered, the respondents are undecided since these may hinder them from achieving their goals. In relation to possible solutions, respondents notice that these possible solutions are effective ways to avoid those problems that the company may encounter in the future.

Overall, there is a significant difference between the profile of the administrative employee respondents and the lead variables. There is a significant difference between the profiles of respondents in terms of compensation and benefits, job satisfaction, and problems encountered and possible solutions, thus rejecting the null hypothesis. Nevertheless, there are insignificant differences revealed in the comparison of civil status and length of service in relation to satisfaction with the job, satisfaction with the shift, satisfaction with employer compensation, organizational commitment, and general opinion. Furthermore, the profile of the administrative employees has an insignificant difference between problems encountered and possible solutions, thus rejecting the null hypothesis.

Company management may maintain a fair number of responsible and young administrative employees they can handle through recruitment and advertising shifts on working hours and training for career development. To possibly increase the satisfaction of the administrative employees regarding their compensation, the company may improve the system of giving bonuses, privileges, and appropriate rewards, be they monetary or non-monetary (e.g., Employee of the Month), as this may add up to an employee's compensation. This will also result in employees being motivated to work. It may be through continuous inquiry and analysis about the state of the salaries, benefits, bonuses, rights, and privileges of their administrative employees for the company to know the specific problems their employees are encountering. Through this, the appropriate department may discover solutions to each problem identified.

Those who handle administrative employees may maintain policies for career development, e.g., giving training, seminars, and other organizational activities. Likewise, they may improve the privileges of the administrative employees that are given by the company. They may also assess the type of working environment of the administrative employees in general by maintaining the sanitation and cleanliness of the vicinity. The administrative employees are also encouraged to stay and enjoy their job and cooperate with their respective supervisors in implementing company policies for the benefit of everyone, especially the employees themselves. Lastly, the researchers recommend further studies on the areas not covered in this research.

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